

Chromatographic migration of cadmium and nickel in different soil types of India

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Abstract : Among heavy metal pollutants cadmium and nickel play major role in polluting environment. So there is a long-term need to investigate the chromatographic migration of these biotoxic heavy metals in soil. In the present work the investigator have chosen three typical profile soil samples of different soil types of India. The study is about the leaching stress and mobility pattern of cadmium and nickel in three selected soil types. Different extractants are used to find out water soluble (water extractable), exchangeable (KNO₃ extractable), available (DTPA extractable) and fixed (HNO₃ extractable) amount of heavy metals in soil. Analysis of ions was done using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. Interpretation of results showed that major portion of heavy metals are retained in the top horizon. It can cause long term toxic effects in plants and animals. Nickel exhibited greater migration properties than that of cadmium. So it will cause greater threat to ground water than that of cadmium.

Keywords : Chromatographic migration, cadmium, nickel, leaching stress.

Introduction

Even in minute concentration heavy metal can cause health hazards to both plants and animals. So there is a long-term need to investigate the movement of biotoxic heavy metals through soil and from the plant root zone into ground water. Most of the heavy metals are firmly fixed in the surface layer of soil, but a small increase in the solubility of soil phase heavy metals results in the deterioration of ground water. The prediction of heavy metal movement is however very complex since it involves numerous chemical reactions in the soil. The mobility of metals in soil is determined by the properties of the metal, the quantity and type of soil adsorption sites, concentration and type of complexing anions (especially H⁺) in soil solution. There is evidence that heavy metals differ in mobility in the soil¹⁻⁴, but little work has been conducted to characterize the mobility of heavy metals in different soil types of India, especially hazardous metals like cadmium and nickel. Cadmium enters into soil through the agricultural applications of sewage sludge, phosphate fertilizers, bordaux mixture, deposition from automobiles,

waste from septic tanks, linked with zinc, industrial pollution, attrition of automobile tyres and combustion of petroleum, coal, paper etc. Nickel is introduced into the environment through sewage sludges, industrial waste products and the release from automobiles. Nickel adsorption takes place easily on soils and its adsorption characteristic related to soil properties⁵. So the present study is conducted to observe the chromatographic migration and leaching stress of cadmium and nickel in three soils having very different chemical and physical properties (Table 1). The results are used to identify the properties of heavy metals in soils that determine metal mobility in soil profiles and thereby to examine the potential hazard of long term surface deposition and accumulation of these elements with respect to their possible movement into the plant root zone or into the ground water storage zone.

Results and discussion

The analytical data (Table 2) show that the leaching loss was more in red sandy loam soil (4.02% for nickel

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of soils

Properties	Soils		
	Laterite	Alluvial	Red sandy loam
Mechanical composition			
(a) Clay (%)	30.36	31.6	21.20
(b) Silt (%)	2.60	7.50	3.60
(c) Fine sand (%)	30.62	22.90	26.60
(d) Coarse sand (%)	36.42	38.00	48.60
pH (1 : 2.5)	5.19	5.60	4.90
Organic carbon (%)	2.00	1.80	0.60
Cation exchange capacity (mg/100 g)	9.80	10.10	3.50
Exchangeable cations (mg/100 g)			
(a) Magnesium	0.44	0.21	0.12
(b) Calcium	0.87	0.32	0.28
(c) Potassium	0.06	0.09	0.15
(d) Sodium	0.08	0.10	0.08

Table 2. Leaching loss of cadmium and nickel under laboratory condition (means over control)

Types of soil	Total loss of metal (mg)	
	Cadmium	Nickel
Laterite	1.887 (0.941%)	3.86 (1.93%)
Alluvial	1.62 (0.81%)	2.647 (1.3%)
Red sandy loam	5.162 (2.5%)	8.024 (4.01%)

and 2.4% for cadmium) compared to other soils. The high leaching loss of heavy metals in red sandy loam soil might be due to its light texture and low content of organic matter (Table 1) which favour the migration down through the soil column⁶. The low leaching loss in alluvial and laterite soils may be due to the fact that these soils contain fairly high amount of clay content which might adsorb higher concentration of applied heavy metal, leaving small fraction for leaching. Hence red sandy loam soil can cause great threat to heavy metal pollution of ground water.

The results of migration studies of cadmium and nickel indicate that heavy metals migrate to a much higher depth in red sandy loam soil than that of the other two soils. The results indicate that potassium nitrate extractable cadmium or exchangeable cadmium accumulated more at 6–8 cm depth in red sandy loam soil (350 $\mu\text{g/g}$) while 2–4 cm depth in laterite soil (328 $\mu\text{g/g}$) and 4–6 cm depth in alluvial soil (340 $\mu\text{g/g}$).

DTPA extractable cadmium (available cadmium) migrates to a higher depth in red sandy loam soil (180 $\mu\text{g/g}$ at 8–10 cm) while both in alluvial and laterite soil, cadmium migrates maximum to a depth of 6–8 cm (310 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 306 $\mu\text{g/g}$).

Nitric acid extractable cadmium (fixed cadmium) was found to be maximum at a depth of 8–10 cm (120 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in red sandy loam soil. But nitric acid extracted cadmium was found to concentrate more at 6–8 cm depth (178 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in alluvial soil. Water extractable metal was mostly found in the top horizon (0–2 cm depth) itself in all soils.

The evaluation of migration pattern of nickel through each column after leaching revealed that nickel migrates to a greater depth than that of cadmium. The sequential analysis shows that potassium nitrate extractable nickel (exchangeable nickel) concentrated more at a depth of 10–12 cm (392 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in red sandy loam soil, 4–6 cm (282 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in laterite soil and 8–10 cm (380 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in alluvial soil.

DTPA extractable nickel (available nickel) concentrated more at a depth of 10–12 cm (294 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in red sandy loam soil while at 6–8 cm depth (280 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in laterite soil and 6–8 cm depth in alluvial soil (360 $\mu\text{g/g}$).

Nitric acid extractable nickel (fixed nickel) was found to accumulate more at 10–12 cm depth (88 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in red sandy loam soil, while it was found to accumulate more at 6–8 cm depth in both laterite and alluvial soils (148 $\mu\text{g/g}$, 143 $\mu\text{g/g}$). Water extractable nickel was found to accumulate at 0–2 cm depth in all soils.

The results of migration studies of cadmium and nickel indicate that heavy metals migrate to a much higher depth in red sandy loam soil than other soils. This may be due to the low organic matter and clay content of red sandy loam soil (Table 1). Low migration of heavy metals in laterite and alluvial soil may be due to its higher CEC, exchangeable base content, clay content and pH (Table 1). Higher organic matter contents retarded cadmium and nickel movement more effectively and the least mobility of metals was observed in mineral soil with relatively high pH, CEC and exchangeable base⁷. Attenuation of cadmium by individual soils varied considerably depending primarily on the clay content and pH⁸. Nickel migrates to a much lower depth of column than that of cadmium. The analysis of soil columns below the depth

of 20 cm show that negligible fraction of heavy metals migrates below the depth of 20 cm, since heavy metals concentrate on the top horizon A and its concentration decreased many fold in B and C horizons⁹. The above results indicate that major portion of heavy metals was retained in the top horizon leaving a small fraction to move downward under the leaching stress. This may be due to the formation of strongly bound insoluble chelates with organic matter or precipitation of metals as insoluble components¹⁰. For those heavy metals that dissolve largely in the form of metal organic complexes, release the metal with dissolved organics may be very different mechanism (possibly biological) than subsequent resorption¹¹. Thus the metal complexes released from the surface soil, where biological activity is high may leach down to subsoil. The lack of retention explains the low subsoil concentration of heavy metals¹².

Since major portion of heavy metals was retained in the top horizon in all soils, it can cause great threat to plants and can cause long term effect on plants and animals. Since nickel exhibited greater migration properties, there may be greater danger of contamination of ground water by this element.

Experimental

Three typical profile soil samples (0–90 cm) of different soil types of India (Kerala in Southern India) i.e. Red sandy loam soil (Kasaragod), alluvial soil (Kannur) and laterite soil (Wayanad) were used in the present investigation.

PVC tubes of 6 cm diameter and one metre length were used for preparing soil columns. Each experiment was done in triplication. These columns were filled with air dried sieved soil samples with gentle tapping to obtain uniform bulk density of 1.3 to 1.4 gm/cc¹³. Bottom ends of these tubes were filled with a tight fitting funnel packed with acid washed glass wool to hold the soil in position. The weight of soil filled in each tube was weighed and recorded. Acid washed sand was spread above the soil column about 0.5 cm thickness to avoid any possible disturbance of the soil surface. The pore volume in respect of each soil column was established before starting the leaching process¹⁰. The total number of leaching was imposed at the rate of one pore volume at each time and average rainfall. After the soil had been uniformly packed

in the column, distilled water was percolated through them overnight in order to ensure uniform water content through out. Each column was then flooded with distilled water, which was kept at 2 cm above the soil surface. At the end of the period, the excess water from the column was drained out. A total of 200 mg of each metal i.e. cadmium or nickel as their water soluble nitrate salt was loaded to each column and was allowed to percolate through the column. The period of leaching was spread over 90 days for all the soil columns. Each time leachate was collected separately and immediately analysed for cadmium or nickel using atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

At the end of the period the soil column was segmented into 2 cm thickness. The wet soil samples were collected and were stored under freeze dried in deep freezer for further analysis. The content of cadmium or nickel were determined by employing sequential extraction technique¹⁰.

5 g samples of soil from each segment were extracted with 25 ml solutions of distilled water, 1 N KNO₃ (pH 7.00), 0.005 M DTPA (pH 7.3) and 1 N HNO₃ sequentially in the order to evaluate water soluble, exchangeable, available and fixed cadmium or nickel accumulated in each segments. The concentration of cadmium or nickel in all extracts was estimated by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. All the experiments were done in triplication.

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